

Fault-tolerant numerical iterative algorithms at scale

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1 Introduction

Large-scale simulation is one of the main tools of modern science. To achieve new scientific challenges, simulations are processed at larger and larger scale. This implies the usage of a multitude of computational units during very large periods of time. As a consequence, High Performance Computing (HPC) experiments are increasingly exposed to errors.

Errors are usually classified in two main categories: fail-stop errors, that are immediately detected, and silent data corruptions, that can be detected through some verification mechanisms [1]. Fail-stop errors correspond to permanent failures, e.g., processor crashes. Silent errors are disruptions that strike and stay undetected until they manifest eventually through strange application behavior. Silent errors arise from two main sources: computation errors and memory bit-flips. Protecting algorithms and softwares from these errors is a major concern of the HPC community. Although there have been many contributions in that direction [2], the design of a resilient holistic methodology ranging from the hardware up to the application is far from having been achieved. For instance, most studies specifically consider only one type of errors, either fail-stop or silent.

This work aims at studying whether numerical algorithms can be protected from all types of errors that can strike at scale, may they be either fail-stop or silent errors. We rely on system-level and numerical state-of-the-art techniques designed for each error type, and we assess whether they can be efficiently combined at scale. We focus on a specific type of algorithms often occurring in numerical simulations, namely iterative schemes. Our comprehensive approach mitigates the impact of all these errors and aims at guaranteeing a correct execution, regardless of the number and nature of errors that will strike. We combine various techniques: detectors for computation errors, checksums for memory errors, and checkpoint/restart for fail-stop errors. We stress that our approach is agnostic of the type, nature and cost of all these techniques.

We design and evaluate a global execution pattern that repeats periodically, where each technique is applied with a specific frequency. In the experimental scenarios that we explore (see Section 5), computation errors strike more frequently than memory errors, which in turn strike more frequently than fail-stop errors. This motivates the shape of the periodic pattern: we perform a certain number of iterations before running a verification for computation errors (chunk). After several chunks, we take a memory checkpoint that would allow us to recover from a memory error (segment). After several segments, we take a (costly) checkpoint on a stable storage in order to be able to recover from fail-stop errors. The size of the chunks, the number of chunks per segment, and the number of segments in the pattern are key parameters of our approach.

Our main contribution is to propose a model for assessing the impact of errors on such iterative schemes, and to derive a pattern allowing us to decide how to optimally trigger the considered system-level and numerical techniques. One classical iterative scheme that motivated this work is the Conjugate Gradient (CG) algorithm. Hence, we perform extensive experiments on several realistic scenarios of executions of CG at scale to assess the impact of each parameter and to demonstrate the impact of the results. The simulator is publicly available for the sake of reproducibility of the results, and to enable further experiments with different execution scenarios.

This report is organized as follows. Section 2 surveys related work. Section 3 outlines the framework with a description of the CG algorithm, and a short presentation of each error source, together with their mitigation techniques. Section 4 is devoted to the design and theoretical analysis of the optimal pattern, which constitutes the heart of our

algorithmic contribution. Section 5 details the experimental framework and reports the results obtained from an extensive set of scenarios. Finally, Section 6 provides concluding remarks and hints for future work.

2 Related work

We survey related work on fault-tolerance in Section 2.1. Then, in Section 2.2, we discuss several papers that focus on the CG algorithm. We conclude with a brief summary in Section 2.3.

2.1 Fault-tolerance techniques

Fault-tolerant approaches cover a wide spectrum of techniques, depending upon the type of errors that are addressed and mitigated.

For fail-stop errors, checkpoint-restart is de-facto standard strategy. Every day, large-scale platforms experience a few failures. After each failure, the application executing on the faulty processor (and likely on many other processors for a large parallel application) is interrupted and must be restarted. Without checkpointing, all the work executed for the application is lost. With checkpointing, the execution can resume from the last checkpoint, after some downtime (enroll a spare to replace the faulty processor) and a recovery (read the checkpoint). Several variants of this policy have been studied; coordinated, hierarchical, multi-level, and in-memory, to name a few; see [1] for an overview. A natural strategy is to checkpoint periodically, and one must decide how often to checkpoint, i.e., derive the optimal checkpointing period. An optimal strategy is defined as a strategy that minimizes the expectation of the execution time of the application. For a preemptible application, where one can checkpoint at any time, the classical formula due to Young [3] and Daly [4] states that the optimal checkpointing period is $\sqrt{2\mu C}$, where μ is the job MTBF (mean time between faults) and C the checkpoint cost.

While fail-stop errors lead to fatal interruptions (such as a crash) and cause the loss of the entire memory of the processor, silent errors, a.k.a. silent data corruptions, only impact a given process and lead to incorrect results. But a silent error strikes undetected and the processor can continue its execution; sometimes the silent error can be detected and corrected, and some other times it degenerates into a fatal fail-stop error. We classify silent errors into two categories: computation errors, which are transient and caused by arithmetic errors in the Arithmetic and Logic Unit (ALU), and memory errors, which are persistent and correspond to bit flips in memory. These bit flips can strike in the dynamic random-access memory (DRAM) due to cosmic radiation, overheat and other sources, but also in the L1 cache which is usually not well protected, or in the L2 cache which might be protected by one parity bit [5, 6, 7, 8].

There are several mathematics mechanisms to detect and correct silent errors, such as parity bits, error correcting codes (ECCs), and Chip-kill technology. They have been implemented to protect the DRAM and different cache layers to some extent. However, the closer the data is to the processing unit, the more frequent the access to that data and therefore the higher the overhead of these methods. Thus, processor caches are not protected by ECC in general, but by weaker mechanisms, like simple parity, exposing a higher risk of undetectable error in case of multiple simultaneous bit flips. Buses also often are a weak link in the protecting chain, making all data transfers at higher risk. In

addition, the constant need to reduce component size and voltage increases the likelihood of silent errors.

Although many silent errors caused by one or multiple bits that spontaneously flip to the opposite state are caught by the above-mentioned hardware mechanisms, in reality, some bit flips still manage to pass undetected [9, 10]. In a nutshell, silent errors have become a major threat due to the increase in problem size [11]: the larger the problem, the more memory to be used to store the data, the more frequent the errors, and the higher the probability of overriding ECC protection, generating multiple errors.

Another major problem with silent errors is *detection latency*: contrarily to a fail-stop error whose detection is immediate, a silent error is identified only when the corrupted data is activated and/or leads to an unusual application behavior. On the contrary, checkpoint and rollback recovery assumes instantaneous error detection, and this raises a new difficulty: if the error stroke before the last checkpoint, and is detected after that checkpoint, then the checkpoint is corrupted and cannot be used to restore the application. To solve this problem, one may envision keeping several checkpoints in memory and restoring the application from the last *valid* checkpoint, thereby rolling back to the last *correct* state of the application [12]. But even if it was at all possible to store many checkpoints (which is very demanding in memory), one would not know how to identify the last valid one. Some verification mechanism, or detector, must be enforced.

Considerable efforts have been directed at designing such verification mechanisms to reveal silent errors, because error detection is usually very costly. Hardware mechanisms, such as ECC memory, can detect and even correct a fraction of errors, but in practice, they are complemented with software techniques. The only general-purpose method is to replicate the execution of the target computational kernel on two sets of processors (i.e., duplication) and to compare the results of both executions. If they do not coincide, an error has been detected, and the application must be executed a third time. To avoid a-posteriori re-execution, triplication can be enforced, which allows for error correction in addition to error detection, using a simple majority vote. However, triplication (originally known as triple modular redundancy and voting [13]) is even more costly than duplication, which already requires half the resources to execute redundant operations.

Application-specific information can be very useful to enable ad-hoc solutions, which dramatically decreases the cost of detection. Many techniques have been advocated. They include memory scrubbing [14] and Algorithm-Based Fault Tolerance (ABFT) techniques [15, 16, 17], such as coding for the sparse-matrix vector multiplication kernel [17], blockwise checksum calculation for error-bounded lossy compressor [18], and coupling a higher-order with a lower-order scheme for PDEs [19]. These methods can only detect an error but do not correct it. Self-stabilizing corrections after error detection in CG are investigated in [20]. Fault-tolerant iterative solvers for sparse linear algebra are introduced in [21, 22, 23], using extra checks such as re-computing inner products of vectors that should be orthogonal, or even re-computing the residual.

Lastly, the idea to use a pattern to position verification and checkpoint is usual, especially when it is not application-specific and when the model deals with multiple sources of errors. It often implies a hierarchy between errors as done for fail-stop errors coming from different sources with only checkpoints [24].

2.2 Protecting the CG algorithm

In this section, we focus on related work on the protection of the CG algorithm. We refer to [2] for a more extensive survey on the resilience of numerical algorithms.

As the detection of a fail-stop error is not bound to the working algorithm, the work looked at the silent errors in CG. Indeed as the word implies, some silent errors can only be detected in regard to the specific algorithm at play. The idea is to draw detection criteria from CG properties. A first criterion is to use a test on the orthogonality of the vectors [25]. Another widely used criterion is the difference between the computed and the true residual [25, 26]. In finite precision arithmetic, these criteria are not necessarily exact, hence the set of a threshold has been investigated. Also, other properties as a property of the matrix [26] or the extensive use of the preconditioner [27] have been proposed in order to reduce the cost of the extra computation and increase the detection. These works rarely discuss about the correction technique after the detection. When it is mentioned, they use checkpoint and rollback technique [25, 26] in order to recover while minimizing the impact of the error. A work [28] goes beyond and optimizes the trade-off of the number of iterations to do before taking a checkpoint in order to minimize the execution time. All these techniques rely completely on the detection of error by the program. Another technique [29] is to not go backward, but instead to try to self-stabilize the algorithm by computing the true residual at regular intervals. However, this could impact the convergence rate in a non predictable way.

2.3 Synthesis

To the best of our knowledge, this work is the first attempt to protect CG from all types of errors: fail-stop, computation and memory. Previous works focused either on an optimal pattern independent from a particular algorithm [24, 30], or were limited to the detection and/or correction of transient errors in CG [27, 26, 28, 29, 25].

3 Framework

We begin by briefly introducing the CG algorithm in Section 3.1. In Section 3.2, we describe the different types of errors that are likely to strike iterative applications. Their detection techniques in the case of the CG algorithm are presented in Section 3.3. Then, Section 3.4 is detailing the model. Finally, the problem that we have tackled during this internship is explained in Section 3.5.

3.1 CG algorithm

The CG algorithm is a method for solving a linear system in an iterative way. The goal is to solve

$$Ax = b,$$

with A a real symmetric positive definite matrix, b and x real vectors with x being the unknown solution. The algorithm uses at iteration i the computed residual r_i , the direction p_i and a coefficient α_i to move x_i toward the solution x of the system [31]. In practice, we will focus on the Preconditioned CG (PCG) algorithm. The preconditioner M related to the A matrix makes convergence faster. The CG algorithm can be seen as PCG using the identity matrix as the preconditioner. The z_i is an added vector useful because

Algorithm 1: PCG algorithm

```
1  $r_0 \leftarrow b - Ax_0$ 
2  $z_0 \leftarrow M^{-1}r_0$ 
3  $p_0 \leftarrow z_0$ 
4  $\gamma_0 \leftarrow r_0^T z_0$ 
5 for  $i = 0 \dots$  until convergence do
6    $\alpha_i \leftarrow \gamma_i / p_i^T A p_i$ 
7    $x_{i+1} \leftarrow x_i + \alpha_i p_i$ 
8    $r_{i+1} \leftarrow r_i - \alpha_i A p_i$ 
9    $z_{i+1} \leftarrow M^{-1}r_{i+1}$ 
10   $\gamma_{i+1} \leftarrow r_{i+1}^T z_{i+1}$ 
11   $\beta_{i+1} \leftarrow \gamma_{i+1} / \gamma_i$ 
12   $p_{i+1} \leftarrow z_{i+1} + \beta_i p_i$ 
```

of the preconditioner. The PCG algorithm can be written as depicted in Algorithm 1. γ_i , α_i , β_i are scalars. The initialisation of the algorithm is on lines [1,4]. The initial guess x_0 is chosen arbitrarily. The first line computes the first residual r_0 . Then, the iteration is on lines [6,12]. At each iteration, the algorithm adds the approximate part of the solution depending on the direction given by the previous iteration, to x_{i+1} . Finally, the new direction p_{i+1} is estimated and conjugated to all previous directions.

3.2 Types of errors

We consider two main categories of errors, the major distinction being how they are detected, following the classical taxonomy [1].

The first category is fail-stop errors, which are detected by a failure of a system that stops the execution. They correspond to permanent failures. If a fail-stop error happens, the execution of the algorithm needs to start again. A classical technique used to protect from such errors is the checkpoint restart technique. Checkpoints are taken periodically, and they store the state of the execution. Then, when an error strikes, a checkpoint can be retrieved and used to restart from the saved state. Hence if a global checkpoint has been taken (i.e., checkpoint of the whole system that does not depend on a hardware that can crash), the execution can start again from this checkpoint instead of starting from the beginning. We use the notation C_{fs} for this type of checkpoint. So the idea in order to protect the algorithm from this type of error is to wait for it to strike and stop the execution and then to rollback to the last checkpoint C_{fs} . We make the hypothesis in the following work that when a fail-stop error strikes, then a crash happens and the execution of the algorithm is immediately stopped (without delay). Also, we assume that no fail stop error can strike during a C_{fs} checkpoint. Both hypotheses ensure that the C_{fs} checkpoint is correct. The hypothesis that a checkpoint is error-free is a classical hypothesis [24, 28].

The second category is silent errors. When a silent error strikes, it has a hidden impact on the execution, for instance by making the output wrong, but it stays undetected if no verification check is done during or at the end of the execution. We choose to divide this category into two types of silent errors: computation errors and memory errors. A computation error is transient and caused by arithmetic errors. For instance, if the execution does the addition $a + b$, where the right result is c , then a computation error

will make the execution output d as the result of this addition, with $c \neq d$. The other type of error is memory error. It corresponds to bit flips in memory. We focus in this work on these types of silent errors.

3.3 Error mitigation techniques for PCG algorithm

As discussed earlier, we aim at protecting PCG from three types of errors.

There are different mechanisms to detect and correct silent errors as stated in the related work (Section 2.1). We choose to rollback when an error is detected. This technique is independent from the chosen algorithm. Furthermore, it is possible to predict the overhead of the execution with the rollbacks. Also, unlike fail-stop errors, silent errors need to be detected. So, there are verification processes during the execution in order to detect these errors. In this work, the verification recall and precision are both one. It means that an error is detected by a verification process if and only if there is an error in the execution at the time of the verification. There is no false positive (a detection of an error when there is none) nor false negative (an error is undetected). Hence, when the verification raises an error, the execution rolls back to the last checkpoint. There is a verification process before any checkpoint, which implies that all checkpoints are valid (error free). In this work, we consider two types of verifications. The first is computation verification V_c . It is completely specific to the application. For CG, it can amount to check the difference between the computed and true residual. The V_c verification detects computation errors and likely some memory errors, at least for CG algorithm. In order to detect all silent errors, the second type of verification process is memory verification V_m . This verification checks the memory. For CG, it is done with a checksum technique. A checksum is a piece of data that results from some computation of a bigger piece of the memory data. It can detect errors by comparing the different checksums of the same piece of data. We choose to consider two different verifications for different possible reasons. The first one is that if there are more computation errors then it is better to execute V_c verifications more often. The second one is that we believe that the computation verification is cheaper than the memory verification. The cost to rollback from a C_{fs} checkpoint is expensive. As the detection of a silent error does not mean a crash in the system, a memory checkpoint C_{cm} is done locally to have a cheaper checkpoint and rollback.

When at least one error is detected, the execution halts and begins the recovery process. It consists of the downtime if applicable, then the rollback to the last checkpoint (loading the last relevant checkpoint). No error can strike during any recovery, should it be a silent error recovery R_{cm} or a fail-stop error recovery R_{fs} . Other hypotheses are needed: every error is detected (it can be at the same verification), no computation error can strike during any verification or checkpoint. It is the same for the memory errors except during the computation verification. As previously stated, fail-stop errors can strike anytime except during a C_{fs} checkpoint. Finally, the entire length of a verification must be executed before it is determined if there is at least one error.

The probability distribution of memory and fail-stop errors both obey an exponential distribution. Let λ_{mem} , λ_{fs} be the parameter for respectively memory errors and fail-stop errors. Hence $e^{-\lambda_{mem}t}$, $e^{-\lambda_{fs}t}$ are respectively the memory, fail-stop probability of successful execution during a duration t (i.e., no error of the specified type strikes during time t). The computation errors follow a geometric distribution of parameter of success per iteration f_{calc} (i.e. no computation error strikes during the iteration). It can be seen as a discrete

Figure 1: Example of a pattern with $n_{fs} = 2$, $n_{cm} = 3$.

exponential law of parameter λ_{calc} with $f_{calc} = e^{-\lambda_{calc}I}$, I is the cost of an iteration. All three error probabilities are considered as mutually independent.

3.4 Model for the pattern

In order to protect CG, there should be verifications and checkpoints interleaved during the execution. The aim is to create a flexible and periodic pattern that depends on the costs of verifications and checkpoints, and on the probabilities of errors. The goal is to minimize the mean time of the entire execution, or equivalently, the expected time per iteration, while effectively protecting CG applications. We choose to have a pattern as the model because it is not bound to the number of iterations the algorithm needs to converge and it is easier to implement as it repeats itself throughout the execution. Also this work considers that computation errors are more likely to strike than memory errors, which in turn are more frequent than fail-stop errors.

We introduce a periodic pattern that mixes checkpoints and verifications of two types. The pattern begins with n_{vc} iterations ($n_{vc} \geq 1$), each taking I time units. After these n_{vc} iterations, we take a V_c verification. This is called a chunk. Then we repeat n_{cm} chunks ($n_{cm} \geq 1$) before executing a V_m verification followed by a C_{cm} checkpoint. All this is called a segment. Thanks to the hypotheses of the last section, the checkpoint is error-free because both verifications are done just before it. We repeat n_{fs} segments ($n_{fs} \leq 1$) followed by a C_{fs} checkpoint. This describes the full pattern. Hence a pattern begins right at the start of the execution or just after the previous pattern with an iteration. It finishes by a C_{fs} checkpoint. Figure 1 provides a graphical representation of a pattern.

In terms of time, $T_{calc} = n_{vc}I + V_c$ is the length of a chunk, $T_{mem} = n_{cm}(n_{vc}I + V_c) + V_m$ is the length of a segment minus the C_{cm} checkpoint and $T_{fs} = n_{fs}(n_{cm}(n_{vc}I + V_c) + V_m + C_{cm})$ is the length of a pattern minus the C_{fs} checkpoint. W is the total work done by the application during the pattern. It corresponds to $W = n_{fs}n_{cm}n_{vc}I$. In this model, it is possible to have an iteration followed by a V_c verification, V_m verification, C_{cm} checkpoint and C_{fs} checkpoint (in that case $n_{vc} = n_{cm} = n_{fs} = 1$). All the notations introduced in this section are summarized in Table 2.

For the PCG algorithm, it means that the work is done during the iterations, then the V_c verification only detects any computation error. The V_m verification detects and corrects any memory error. The C_{cm} checkpoint stores only the vectors, while the C_{fs} checkpoint stores also the matrix and preconditioner.

About the assumption that there are likely more computation errors than memory

errors, the pattern is not bound to the specific type of silent errors, so if the assumption is incorrect in some contexts, we believe the pattern also works if we swap verification techniques and use a different shape.

3.5 The problem

We have a model, now we would like to find the optimal pattern. Indeed, the unknown parts of the pattern are the values of the three parameters (n_{vc}, n_{cm}, n_{fs}) . To design an efficient pattern, there are two added overheads to the regular work $W = n_{fs}n_{cm}n_{vc}I$ of the pattern. The first overhead is the cost of the verifications and checkpoints between the iterations. And the second overhead is the cost of recovery after the strike of an error. We need to find the balance between these two added costs. In order to do that, we will derive a formula of the mean time E needed to complete the pattern. E depends on (n_{vc}, n_{cm}, n_{fs}) . The goal is to minimize the expected time per iteration:

$$\min \frac{E(n_{fs}, n_{cm}, n_{vc})}{W} = \min \frac{E(n_{fs}, n_{cm}, n_{vc})}{n_{fs}n_{cm}n_{vc}I}.$$

4 Optimal pattern

In order to find the optimal pattern from the model, we compute the expected time per iteration, and then find the pattern with minimum overhead. This gives the optimal pattern with (n_{vc}, n_{cm}, n_{fs}) . First we introduce some notations in Section 4.1. Then we consider the formula for the complete problem with a full pattern in Section 4.2.

4.1 Useful notations

To simplify forthcoming formulas, we introduce notations for probabilities. Let z denote one of *calc* for computation error distribution, or *mem* for memory error distribution or *fs* for fail-stop error distribution. Let P_{succ}^z be the probability of success of the z error distribution. By definition, $P_{fail}^z = 1 - P_{succ}^z$, is the probability for the whole segment (for the parts in which an error of type z can strike), except for $P_{fail}^{calc}(i)$, which is the probability that the first computation error strikes (and is detected) at the i th chunk of the segment for $1 \leq i \leq n_{cm}$. We have $P_{succ}^{fs, mem, calc} = P_{succ}^{fs} P_{succ}^{mem} P_{succ}^{calc}$. Lastly, let $1 - P_{no.fs}$ be the probability that the first error in the segment is a fail-stop error.

4.2 Mean time computation of a pattern

We now consider the problem with all three types of errors. We want to find E the mean time of a pattern with a given n_{vc}, n_{cm}, n_{fs} . The execution of the pattern starts right after the C_{cm} and C_{fs} checkpoints. If the execution is error-free, it will firstly do a chunk of n_{vc} iterations I finishing by a V_c iteration. It will go through n_{cm} of those exact same chunks before executing a V_m verification, then a C_{cm} checkpoint to complete the first segment. n_{fs} segments are executed before taking a C_{fs} checkpoint which is the end of the pattern. However, if the execution is not error-free, the difficulty lies in the different recovery processes depending upon whether the error that strikes/is detected is a silent or fail-stop error, because the checkpoints are different. So the time it takes to recover from a silent error is not the same as for a fail-stop error. We have to break down the E formula

into parts in order to tackle this problem of different rollbacks to different checkpoints. Let E_k be the mean time to complete segment k (i.e. to attain the C_{fs} checkpoint for $0 \leq k < n_{fs}$). If a silent error is detected, then only the current segment is restarted. If a fail-stop error is detected, then all the i segments for $i < k$ have to be completed again and then the current segment k is restarted. In order to complete the pattern, all segments must be completed. So we have the relation:

$$E = \sum_{i=0}^{n_{fs}-1} E_i + C_{fs} \quad (4.2.1)$$

The formula for E_k is obtained by distinguishing among four cases depending on the error events. We look at the first potential error because upon detection, the program will rollback to the last checkpoint and it will start again. All the events have a different outcome in terms of overhead.

Case 1 is when no error struck during the computation of the pattern. So it is the probability of no error of any type (success) with the time it takes to compute once the whole pattern (iterations, verifications and checkpoints). Case 2 is when the first error to be spotted is a memory bit-flip. It means no fail-stop nor computation error happened before the end of the memory verification which is done once at the end of the pattern before the computation/memory checkpoint. Case 3 is when the first error to be spotted is a computation error. This type of error can strike only during the iterations. The lost time created by this error depends on the chunk where it happened. If a memory error happens anytime during the computation of the segment, in this case the program will not know as the computation error will be the first to be found. Case 4 is when the first error to strike is a fail-stop, so it is immediately spotted. E_{lost} is the lost time expectation during the segment when the failure strikes. When this error strikes, the program needs to start again at the beginning of the pattern, so all the previous completed segments of the pattern have to be done again. As a reminder, $1 - P_{no_fs}$ is the probability that the first error to be spotted is a fail-stop error.

$$E_k = P_{succ}^{fs,mem,calc} [T_{mem} + C_{cm}] \quad (\text{Case 1})$$

$$+ P_{fail}^{mem} P_{succ}^{calc} P_{succ}^{fs} [T_{mem} + R_{cm} + E_k] \quad (\text{Case 2})$$

$$+ \sum_{i=1}^{n_{cm}} P_{fail}^{calc}(i) P_{succ}^{fs}(i) [iT_{calc} + R_{cm} + E_k] \quad (\text{Case 3})$$

$$+ (1 - P_{no_fs}) [E_{lost} + R_{fs} + \sum_{i=0}^k E_i] \quad (\text{Case 4})$$

Detailed computation of some parts of the formula:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{cm}} P_{fail}^{calc}(i) [iT_{calc}] &= (1 - f_{calc}^{nvc}) [T_{calc}] \sum_{i=1}^{n_{cm}} i f_{calc}^{nvc(i-1)} \\ &= [T_{calc}] \frac{n_{cm} f_{calc}^{nvc(n_{cm}+1)} - (n_{cm} + 1) f_{calc}^{nvc n_{cm}} + 1}{1 - f_{calc}^{nvc}} \end{aligned} \quad (4.2.2)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{i=1}^{n_{cm}} P_{fail}^{calc}(i) P_{succ}^{fs}(i) &= \sum_{i=1}^{n_{cm}} (1 - f_{calc}^{n_{vc}}) f_{calc}^{n_{vc}(i-1)} e^{-\lambda_{fs} T_{calc} i} \\
&= (1 - f_{calc}^{n_{vc}}) e^{-\lambda_{fs} T_{calc}} \sum_{i=0}^{n_{cm}-1} (f_{calc}^{n_{vc}} e^{-\lambda_{fs} T_{calc}})^i \\
&= (1 - f_{calc}^{n_{vc}}) e^{-\lambda_{fs} T_{calc}} \left(\frac{(f_{calc}^{n_{vc}} e^{-\lambda_{fs} T_{calc}})^{n_{cm}} - 1}{f_{calc}^{n_{vc}} e^{-\lambda_{fs} T_{calc}} - 1} \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{4.2.3}$$

With P_{no_fs} :

$$\begin{aligned}
P_{no_fs} &= P_{succ}^{fs,mem,calc} + P_{fail}^{mem} P_{succ}^{calc} P_{succ}^{fs} + \sum_{i=1}^{n_{cm}} P_{fail}^{calc}(i) P_{succ}^{fs}(i) \\
&= e^{-T_{mem}(\lambda_{fs} + \lambda_{mem}) - C_{cm} \lambda_{fs}} (f_{calc})^{n_{vc} n_{cm}} \\
&\quad + (1 - e^{-\lambda_{mem} T_{mem}}) e^{-\lambda_{fs} T_{mem}} (f_{calc})^{n_{vc} n_{cm}} \\
&\quad + (1 - f_{calc}^{n_{vc}}) e^{-\lambda_{fs} T_{calc}} \left(\frac{(f_{calc}^{n_{vc}} e^{-\lambda_{fs} T_{calc}})^{n_{cm}} - 1}{f_{calc}^{n_{vc}} e^{-\lambda_{fs} T_{calc}} - 1} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

E_{lost} , let X be this random variable following the exponential distribution of parameter λ_{fs} (we follow the same computation than [30]):

$$\begin{aligned}
E_{lost} &= \int_0^{\infty} x P(X = x | X < T_{mem} + C_{cm}) dx \\
&= \int_0^{T_{mem} + C_{cm}} x \frac{P(X = x)}{P(X < T_{mem} + C_{cm})} dx \\
&= \frac{1}{1 - e^{-\lambda_{fs}(T_{mem} + C_{cm})}} \int_0^{T_{mem} + C_{cm}} x \lambda_{fs} e^{-\lambda_{fs} x} dx \\
&= \frac{1}{\lambda_{fs}} - \frac{T_{mem} + C_{cm}}{e^{\lambda_{fs}(T_{mem} + C_{cm})} - 1}
\end{aligned}$$

Let M be the part that does not depend of k , i.e., the common part between all segments (see Equation (4.2.2) and Equation (4.2.3) for calculus part):

$$\begin{aligned}
M &= P_{succ}^{fs,mem,calc} [T_{mem} + C_{cm}] \\
&\quad + P_{fail}^{mem} P_{succ}^{calc} P_{succ}^{fs} [T_{mem} + R_{cm}] \\
&\quad + \sum_{i=1}^{n_{cm}} P_{fail}^{calc}(i) P_{succ}^{fs}(i) [R_{cm}] \\
&\quad + \sum_{i=1}^{n_{cm}} P_{fail}^{calc}(i) P_{succ}^{fs}(i) [i(T_{calc})] \\
&\quad + (1 - P_{no_fs}) [E_{lost} + R_{fs}]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M &= e^{-(n_{cm}(n_{vc}I+V_c)+V_m)(\lambda_{fs}+\lambda_{mem})-C_{cm}\lambda_{fs}} (f_{calc})^{n_{vc}n_{cm}} [n_{cm}(n_{vc}I+V_c) + V_m + C_{cm}] \\
&+ (1 - e^{-\lambda_{mem}(n_{cm}(n_{vc}I+V_c)+V_m)}) e^{-\lambda_{fs}(n_{cm}(n_{vc}I+V_c)+V_m)} (f_{calc})^{n_{vc}n_{cm}} [n_{cm}(n_{vc}I+V_c) + V_m + R_{cm}] \\
&+ (1 - f_{calc}^{n_{vc}}) e^{-\lambda_{fs}T_{calc}} \left(\frac{(f_{calc}^{n_{vc}} e^{-\lambda_{fs}T_{calc}})^{n_{cm}} - 1}{f_{calc}^{n_{vc}} e^{-\lambda_{fs}T_{calc}} - 1} \right) [R_{cm}] \\
&+ (1 - f_{calc}^{n_{vc}}) e^{-\lambda_{fs}T_{calc}} \left(\frac{(f_{calc}^{n_{vc}} e^{-\lambda_{fs}T_{calc}})^{n_{cm}} (n_{cm}(f_{calc}^{n_{vc}} e^{-\lambda_{fs}T_{calc}} - 1) - 1) + 1}{(f_{calc}^{n_{vc}} e^{-\lambda_{fs}T_{calc}} - 1)^2} \right) [(n_{vc}I + V_c)] \\
&+ [1 - [e^{-(n_{cm}(n_{vc}I+V_c)+V_m)(\lambda_{fs}+\lambda_{mem})-C_{cm}\lambda_{fs}} (f_{calc})^{n_{vc}n_{cm}} \\
&+ (1 - e^{-\lambda_{mem}(n_{cm}(n_{vc}I+V_c)+V_m)}) e^{-\lambda_{fs}(n_{cm}(n_{vc}I+V_c)+V_m)} (f_{calc})^{n_{vc}n_{cm}} \\
&+ (1 - f_{calc}^{n_{vc}}) e^{-\lambda_{fs}T_{calc}} \left(\frac{(f_{calc}^{n_{vc}} e^{-\lambda_{fs}T_{calc}})^{n_{cm}} - 1}{f_{calc}^{n_{vc}} e^{-\lambda_{fs}T_{calc}} - 1} \right)]] \left[\frac{1}{\lambda_{fs}} - \frac{n_{cm}(n_{vc}I + V_c) + V_m + C_{cm}}{e^{\lambda_{fs}(n_{cm}(n_{vc}I+V_c)+V_m+C_{cm})} - 1} + R_{fs} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

Explicit formula for E_k :

$$\begin{aligned}
E_k &= M + (1 - P_{no_fs}) \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} E_i + (1 - P_{succ}^{fs,mem,calc}) E_k \\
&= \frac{M}{P_{succ}^{fs,mem,calc}} \left(\frac{1 - P_{no_fs}}{P_{succ}^{fs,mem,calc}} + 1 \right)^k
\end{aligned} \tag{4.2.4}$$

The proof of Equation (4.2.4) easily follows from induction on k :

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned}
E_0 &= \frac{M}{P_{succ}^{fs,mem,calc}} \\
&= \frac{M}{P_{succ}^{fs,mem,calc}} \left(\frac{1 - P_{no_fs}}{P_{succ}^{fs,mem,calc}} + 1 \right)^0
\end{aligned}$$

For k , we have for all $i \in 0, 1, \dots, k-1$ the formula is true :

$$\begin{aligned}
E_k &= \frac{M}{P_{succ}^{fs,mem,calc}} + \frac{(1 - P_{no_fs})}{P_{succ}^{fs,mem,calc}} \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} \frac{M}{P_{succ}^{fs,mem,calc}} \left(\frac{1 - P_{no_fs}}{P_{succ}^{fs,mem,calc}} + 1 \right)^i \\
&= \frac{M}{P_{succ}^{fs,mem,calc}} \left(1 + \frac{(1 - P_{no_fs})}{P_{succ}^{fs,mem,calc}} \frac{\left(\frac{1 - P_{no_fs}}{P_{succ}^{fs,mem,calc}} + 1 \right)^k - 1}{\frac{1 - P_{no_fs}}{P_{succ}^{fs,mem,calc}} + 1 - 1} \right) \\
&= \frac{M}{P_{succ}^{fs,mem,calc}} \left(\frac{1 - P_{no_fs}}{P_{succ}^{fs,mem,calc}} + 1 \right)^k
\end{aligned}$$

□

Explicit formula for E :

$$\begin{aligned}
E &= \sum_{k=0}^{n_{fs}-1} E_k + C_{fs} \\
&= \frac{M}{1 - P_{no_fs}} \left[\left(\frac{1 - P_{no_fs}}{P_{succ}^{fs,mem,calc}} + 1 \right)^{n_{fs}} - 1 \right] + C_{fs}
\end{aligned} \tag{4.2.5}$$

E is finally determined! We aimed at minimizing E analytically, as a function of variables n_{vc}, n_{cm}, n_{fs} . However, the formula is too complex, and we have to compute E numerically. Given application and resilience parameters, we compute the mean time with instantiations of the PCG algorithm in order to find the values of n_{vc}, n_{cm}, n_{fs} that minimize the expected time of the pattern. We introduce the naive model which is our model with $n_{vc} = n_{cm} = n_{fs} = 1$. It means that after each iteration, both verifications and checkpoints are taken. This naive approach is often the first approach to create a fault-tolerant algorithm [27].

5 Experiments

The code used for the outputs of this section is publicly available at https://gitlab.aliens-lyon.fr/atremode/code_stage_m2.git.

The formula needs data for the values of the different platform, application and resilience variables (excluding n_{vc}, n_{cm}, n_{fs}). We instantiate different scenarios (set of values for these variables) to analyse the behavior of the expected time per iteration. These are the experiments with the mean time of the pattern. The aim is to see if the model and its minimization are interesting in the context of our work. The naive approach is one potential comparison. Section 5.1 provides details about the experimental settings. Then Section 5.2 presents the different scenarios that we are experimenting with. Lastly, the results and analyses of the scenarios are given in Section 5.3.

5.1 Code settings

The experiments have been coded in Python 3. Given a scenario which provides a set of values for all variables, the goal is to find the triplet (n_{vc}, n_{cm}, n_{fs}) that minimizes the mean time of the pattern E . We choose to make it dependent of the MTBF (mean time between failures) of the errors. Hence the output of the experiment is a figure of x , a parameter involved in the MTBF of errors, and of $\min_{(n_{vc}, n_{cm}, n_{fs})} \frac{E(x, n_{vc}, n_{cm}, n_{fs})}{W}$ the overhead of the function with $W = n_{fs} n_{cm} n_{vc} I$. Each point shows the value of (n_{vc}, n_{cm}, n_{fs}) that reaches the minimum for a given x . It is helped by the fact that (n_{vc}, n_{cm}, n_{fs}) are positive integers. So the code computes the overhead for each possibility of (n_{vc}, n_{cm}, n_{fs}) chosen by the user (there is a given customised interval for each with a step). The code stores only the minimum value for each x .

5.2 Scenarios for the experiments

We test the optimisation of the pattern to different scenarios. All scenarios use the PCG algorithm shown in Algorithm 1. A scenario is a coherent set of variable of E (except for n_{vc}, n_{cm}, n_{fs} , which are the unknowns we want to set in order to reach the minimum, and $f_{calc}, \lambda_{mem}, \lambda_{fs}$, which are computed as a function of x). All the scenarios have the same choice for the techniques used. The idea is as follows: we want to solve a diffusion equation in 3D. The matrix A is sparse. For the machine part, we consider the Frontier supercomputer, localised in the Oak Ridge National Laboratory, TN, USA. It is the first exascale supercomputer (i.e., capable of 10^{18} floating point operations per second (flops)). For the verification, the computation is performed using two criteria described in [26], namely the alpha verification and the residual gap norm. The memory verification is done with a checksum technique [32]. The memory checkpoint stores only the vectors,

while the fail-stop checkpoint stores the matrix and the preconditioner in addition to the vectors.

The scenarios were made thanks to the inputs of experts in HPC and PCG, namely Emmanuel Agullo, Luc Giraud and Thomas Herault.

5.2.1 Error probability distribution

There is limited information about potential values for any error probability that we are interested in. We look at the mean time between failures (MTBF), a metric that in our case is the mean time between the strikes of two errors of the same type. Note that the MTBF depends on the machine the application is run.

There are good sources of information for fail-stop errors in the literature. The $MTBF(fs)$ of recent leadership HPC machines is usually of a few hours [1, 33, 34, 35, 36]. We will typically consider the range of 1h to 8h. However for memory and computation errors, there is no extensive data on them to the best of our knowledge. Hence we do not have precise values for the probability parameters. We decide to introduce a new parameter x . We say that $MTBF(fs) = x$, $MTBF(mem) = \frac{x}{2}$, $MTBF(calc) = \frac{x}{20}$. It means that $\lambda_{fs} = \frac{1}{x}$, $\lambda_{mem} = \frac{2}{x}$ and $f_{calc} = e^{-\frac{20}{x}}$.

We made this choice because if the majority of errors are fail-stop errors then the system would either be really secure or not reliable. And so we do not think our model would help in these cases. Then even if we say that there is computation errors and memory errors, it can be difficult in the execution to differentiate the two of them. There is a chance that what we call memory error is caught during the computation verification as it is the first verification to be encountered. So we decide that the MTBF of computation errors is shorter than the MBTF of memory errors.

5.2.2 Scenario 1: Ideal world

The first scenario is the set of values that fits a theoretical model. We extrapolate the values to our application. We base the values on an asymptotic analysis.

First, there is the cost of the PCG algorithm. We consider integer or double for number storage. We chose a specific PCG model: we want to solve a 3D diffusion discretized on a Cartesian grid using a 7 point stencil on a cube of side m . It means that we consider a point and its six neighbors in the cube. The size of the square matrix A is $N = m^3$ rows and N columns. The matrix is sparse and contains $7N$ non zero elements. The matrix is in COO (COOrdinates) storage. This structure is made of three tables of the rows, columns and index. The total cost of the A matrix in COO storage is of $7N$ real numbers plus $14N$ integers. It translates to $21 \times 8 \times N$ bytes. The preconditioner M is a cycle of geometric multigrid. M is composed of a sequence of three operators, namely the coarse discretization, the restriction and the interpolation, with an asymptotic memory footprint of $72 \times 3 \times 8 \times N$ bytes. In addition, there are five vectors (b, x, r, p, z) in the PCG algorithm 1, each of size N . It means $5 \times 8 \times N$ bytes in memory. So the PCG algorithm uses in memory at least $(21 + 24 \times 3 + 5) \times 8 \times N$ bytes, so approximately $800N$ bytes.

Regarding an iteration, we consider that the cost comes mostly from the matrix-vector product and the preconditioner application. The matrix-vector product for sparse matrix takes $13N$. The preconditioner costs is approximately $70N$. In addition to the other computations, the cost of one iteration is approximately of $100N$.

Then, the PCG application runs with parallelism. Let p be the number of processors used for the application. The problem is partitioned across the p processors. The following values are taken according to Frontier data. Then the number of processors of Frontier used is $p = 10^4$ (64 cores and 8 GPU per node). We can also count the number of processes, with 8 processes per node. First, the size of the problem m is set between 10^3 and 10^4 . Afterwards, we need the time it takes to do a particular operation τ for the machine. The first one is the computing-bound operation per processor $\tau_{cpu} = 3.2e13$ flops per second. The second one is the memory-bound operation per processor $\tau_{mem} = 1.6e12$ bytes per second (hence to be divided by 8 for doubles). The third one is the checkpoint filesystem for the whole machine $\tau_{fs} = [4.5e10, 4.5e12]$ bytes per second.

Now, we compose with all the values above to set the variables. The result of this is found in Table 3. The iteration cost is $I = \frac{100N}{8p\tau_{mem}}$. For the computing verification, the alpha verification cost is negligible, while the residual gap is composed of a sparse matrix-vector product ($13N$) and two vector-vector difference of size N . In total, the value is $V_c = \frac{15m^3}{p\tau_{cpu}}$ for the computation verification. The memory verification is done for all the vectors (b, x, r, p, z) , the matrix A and the preconditioner M . We consider that the checksum technique used is linear to the size of the structures. So we consider that $V_m = \frac{800N}{8p\tau_{mem}}$. For the checkpoints, the memory checkpoint stores locally the vectors (one checkpoint per processors) hence $C_{cm} = \frac{40N}{8p\tau_{mem}}$. The fail-stop checkpoint is global for all processors involved in the application and stores the vectors, the matrix and the preconditioner, hence $C_{fs} = \frac{800N}{\tau_{fs}}$. Lastly, the silent error recovery R_{cm} has the same cost as the C_{cm} checkpoint as we take the best case scenario, with the downtime being zero. We choose to do this because it is impossible to give a value to the downtime. It is the same with the fail-stop error recovery R_{fs} .

The values coming from these computations are found in Table 1. These numbers are very optimistic because it is directly derived from the theoretical values. For instance, the communication between the nodes are not really taken into account. Further discussions with experts in the domain and review of the literature [37, 38] show that more realistic values would be much larger. Hence we need other scenarios.

5.2.3 Scenario 2 and 3: A more realistic approach

Next we wanted to have more realistic scenarios like ones following the initial idea with PCG application at scale. We were not able to find this precise scenario in the literature. However, we extrapolate two scenarios from papers that are near from our initial idea.

The scenario 2 is partially taken from [37]. We have $N = 3.6 \times 10^{12}$ unknowns for the size of the problem and 3×10^3 nodes. Then we extrapolate that for one iteration, there is 10 seconds for the preconditioner, 2 seconds for the matrix-vector product and 1 seconds for the other operations. It means that one iteration takes 13 seconds. Moreover, the cost of the computation verification is set by the cost of the matrix-vector product, then $V_c = 2$ seconds. For the other values, we deduce them using the size of the problem, the time of the computation and the balance that appears in scenario 1. Hence, the cost to copy vectors in the local memory means that $C_{cm} = 0.5$ seconds and so $R_{cm} = C_{cm}$ by hypothesis. The fail-stop checkpoint is global so $C_{fs} = 180$ seconds and $R_{fs} = C_{fs}$. Lastly, the checksum cost implies that $V_m = 6seconds$.

Compared to scenario 1, the size of the problem is similar, but there are 10 times less nodes. The iteration time is near 10 seconds for scenario 2 instead of 10^{-3} seconds for scenario 1.

The scenario 3 has a larger cost for one iteration. The values for the computation come from [38]. The size of the problem is $N = 1.1 \times 10^{13}$ and the number of nodes is 2×10^4 . one iteration takes 110 seconds. It is composed of 85 seconds for the preconditioner, 17 seconds for the matrix-vector product and 8 seconds for the other operations. The computation verification is the nearly the cost of one matrix-vector product, $V_c = 17$ seconds. Then, even if the size of the problem is 3 times bigger than scenario 2, there are 6 times more nodes. Hence, the local checkpoint is quick, $C_{cm} = 0.25$ seconds and $R_{fs} = C_{cm}$. The memory verification takes $V_m = 3$ seconds. Lastly, the fail-stop checkpoint is costlier because of the number of nodes and unknowns of the problem, $C_{fs} = 540$ and $R_{fs} = C_{fs}$.

A summary of all the values for each scenario is found on Table 1.

Scenario	Ideal PCG with fs	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Size of the problem	10^{12}	3.6×10^{12}	1.1×10^{13}
Number of nodes	10^4	3×10^3	2×10^4
I	7.8125×10^{-4}	13	110
V_c	5.8594×10^{-6}	2	17
V_m	6.25×10^{-3}	6	3
C_{cm}	3.125×10^{-4}	0.5	0.25
R_{cm}	3.125×10^{-4}	0.5	0.25
C_{fs}	1.7778×10^2	180	540
R_{fs}	1.7778×10^2	180	540
	second	second	second

Table 1: Values of variables for different scenarios for PCG algorithm.

5.3 Results

The mean time is instantiated with the three scenarios. The outputs are shown on Figure 2 for scenario 1, 3 for scenario 2 and 4 for scenario 3. The mean time for the naive model ($n_{vc} = n_{cm} = n_{fs} = 1$) for scenario 2 and 3 appears on Figure 5.

The x-axis is for the error parameter x . The unit is the fail-stop MTBF in hour (MTBF of memory error is divided by two and twenty for computation error). When x increases, the errors are less likely to strike. The y-axis is the overhead. We measure the average of added costs consisting on the impact of errors on the algorithm with the recoveries and the added cost of the checkpoints and verifications that protect the algorithm. A value of one means that there is no added cost, so it is only the cost of the iterations of the pattern (when there is no error). It is safe to say that the overhead decreases when the MTBF increases as less errors means less recoveries and less need to take verifications and checkpoints as often. Lastly, the triplets of number that appears on the curve are (n_{vc}, n_{cm}, n_{fs}) that correspond respectively to the number of iterations in a chunk, the number of chunks and the number of segments in the pattern. The output of multiplication of these three variables is the number of iterations for the optimal pattern regarding the error probabilities.

The result of scenario 1 (Figure 2) is interesting, indeed the overhead is less than 1.4 for all the tested values. However, in the context of the PCG algorithm there is a problem, it is the number of iterations in a pattern. For $x = 4$ hours, there are $116 \times 31 \times 758 \approx 2 \times 10^6$ iterations in a pattern. A simple CG algorithm in exact arithmetic takes at most the size of the problem as the number of iterations to converge. It converges even faster with the

Figure 2: Results for Scenario 1.

Figure 3: Results for Scenario 2.

Figure 4: Results for Scenario 3.

Figure 5: Naive approach for Scenarios 2 and 3.

help of a preconditioner. Even if the problem is in floating point arithmetic, the PCG algorithm will likely finish before taking the first fail-stop checkpoint in the case of scenario 1. We can see that one iteration is really quick ($\approx 10^{-3}$ seconds) compared to taking a fail-stop checkpoint ($\approx 10^2$ seconds). It seems likely that the time of communication and synchronization between the nodes have been overlooked. As this scenario is completely theoretical for the values, we cannot draw conclusion regarding the model without looking at the other scenarios.

Scenario 2 has a more realist background. For $x = 4$ hours, there are 132 iterations in a pattern. The pattern is illustrated on Figure 6. The difference with scenario 1 can be explained because the cost of one iteration is more expensive than the one in scenario 1 while the cost of a fail-stop checkpoint is similar (and the other costs are less than the one of the iterations). We have results but we need some comparison to show that it is optimized. The idea is to compare it with the naive pattern, when there is an iteration than the verifications and checkpoints just after ($n_{vc} = n_{cm} = n_{fs} = 1$). The result is shown in Figure 5. In the case of scenario 2, the average overhead for the naive pattern is nearly 16. It means that the minimum overhead from the experiment is at least 8 times better than the overhead of the naive pattern.

Moreover, we wanted to see the influence of the coefficients of the error probabilities. Indeed, we decided to set them to a fixed value that does not necessarily have a realistic background. It is the case for the silent errors as there is so little data for their MTBF. We perform another experiment where we choose $x = 4$ hours, $MTBF(fs) = x$ (it does not change), but we set $coef_{calc}$ and $coef_{mem}$ as the variables with $MTBF(calc) = \frac{x}{coef_{calc}}$ and $MTBF(mem) = \frac{x}{coef_{mem}}$. The result is shown on Figure 7. The link with the probabilities is that $\lambda = \frac{1}{MTBF}$ for the exponential distribution. The graphic shows that the coefficients have obviously an impact on the minimum overhead (it has an impact of the average number of errors that strike), but not necessarily an outstanding impact.

Figure 6: Exemple of the minimal pattern from Figure 3 when $x = 4$ hours.

Figure 7: Scenario 2, $x = 4$ hours. Impact of the coefficient of silent error probabilities.

Scenario 3 shows a limit of the model. Indeed for silent errors, it looks like the naive model. In this scenario, the cost of an iteration is the most expensive one of all scenarios and even if the cost of the fail-stop checkpoint is also the largest, the cost of the memory verification and checkpoint are lower than in scenario 2 because there is a difference in the number of nodes. The minimum overhead of the experiment is two times better than the overhead of the naive pattern. This essentially shows that fail-stop errors stay the major interest as it costs more in terms of protection.

The results show that the model is interesting in order to protect PCG algorithm from fail-stop and silent errors compared to a more naive or systematic approach.

6 Conclusion

The main contribution of this work is the design and analysis of a new flexible approach to protect numerical iterative algorithms against three types of errors: fail-stop, memory and computation errors. We introduce a hierarchical pattern and compute the mean time per iteration within that pattern, enabling to optimize it. Lastly, we instantiate the model with different scenarios that show that our model is much better than the naive approach. To the best of our knowledge, simpler patterns have been introduced for simpler models in the literature, but it is the first time where all the three error types are dealt with, at the price of a very complicated derivation for the expected time per iteration.

For future work, we want to make the model more realistic, so we need to loosen some of the hypotheses. The model assumes a clear distinction between errors whether it be their types or their consequences. One of the most restrictive hypothesis is to assume that verifications have a recall and precision of 1, hence checkpoints are error-free. In the framework of iterative numerical algorithms, verifications are not perfect, so future work could be devoted to perform multiple rollbacks until an error-free checkpoint is identified. Furthermore, even if the experiments show the appeal of our model, they lack real data that completely fit the requirements. Lastly, the model is instantiated for the

PCG algorithm, but we believe it can well be used for other iterative algorithms. Indeed, the approach is agnostic of the precise nature and type of the various verifications and checkpoints.

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7 Appendix

Symbol	Definition	Symbol	Definition
I	One iteration	n_{vc}	Number of iterations in a chunk
V_c	Computation verification	n_{cm}	Number of chunks in a segment
V_m	Memory verification	n_{fs}	Number of segments in a pattern
C_{cm}	Local memory checkpoint (vectors of the algorithm)	T_{calc}	$= n_{vc}I + V_c$
C_{fs}	Checkpoint (in case of a fail-stop error)	T_{mem}	$= n_{cm}(n_{vc}I + V_c) + V_m$
R_{cm}	Local recovery process from C_{cm} checkpoint	T_{fs}	$= n_{fs}(n_{cm}(n_{vc}I + V_c) + V_m + C_{cm})$
R_{fs}	Recovery process from C_{fs} checkpoint	W	$= n_{fs}n_{cm}n_{vc}I$
P_{succ}^z	Probability of no error of type z	f_{calc}	Parameter of geometric distrib. for computation error
P_{fail}^z	$= 1 - P_{succ}^z$	λ_{mem}	Parameter of exponential distrib. for memory error
$P_{fail}^{calc}(i)$	Proba. that first computation error is in chunk i of segment	λ_{fs}	Parameter of exponential distrib. for fail-stop error
P_{no_fs}	$1 - P_{no_fs}$: the first error to strike is a fail-stop error		

Table 2: Notations of Section 3.

Variable	Value	Variable	Value
V_c	$= \frac{15N}{8p\tau_{cpu}}$	I	$= \frac{100N}{8p\tau_{mem}}$
V_m	$= \frac{800N}{8p\tau_{mem}}$	C_{fs}	$= \frac{800N}{\tau_{fs}}$
C_{cm}	$= \frac{40N}{8p\tau_{mem}}$	R_{fs}	$= C_{fs}$
R_{cm}	$= C_{cm}$		

Table 3: Expression for scenario with ideal PCG.